

Democracy Towards Good Governance: Study of critical factors distressing the Democracy in Pakistan.

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Abstract.

Since inception of Pakistan in 1947, the country has gone through autocratic systems and fragile democratic systems. During 65 years history of Pakistan, 40 years has been ruled by non-democratic rulers and 25 years have been ruled by fragile democratic people. It has been 40 years since the introduction of parliamentary form of democratic system but it has brought no improvement in nourishing the democratic values overall. It is undeniable fact that real representatives in democracy can move forward the democratic values

Geographically, the population of the country is living in urban areas and rural areas. According the Government statistics, 60% population is living in rural areas and 40% is living in the urban areas. The country is treading towards prosperity and development of the nation, no matter how far it may be slow taking process. The democratic system controlled by few privileged class of people does not truly representing the aspiration of the masses and consequently it does left good omen for the future of the nation.

*This research study is focused on the analyzing that how far our prevailing democratic system fall under the essence of democratic system and what are the critical factors affecting the essence of democracy in the country. **Abraham Lincoln in his speech on November, 19, 1963 has described democracy in the following words; Government of the people, for the people and by the people**” .The research study will be taken on the basis of above three mentioned hypotheses of democracy essence i.e **Government by the People, Government for the People and Government of the People.***

This research study has targeted the common voters in the various districts of Pakistan and conducted survey from the targeted population in rural and urban areas for the purpose of collecting information.

Keywords: Democracy, Good Governance, Rural Population, Urban population, Political parties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Democracy is the political system which is composed of two Latin words. “Demos” means people and “Kratos” means government of the people. According to Thomas Hobbes, in democracy “the real power of Sovereignty lies in the hands of common people. The history of democracy has showed that the people of ancient Athens implemented ideal form of democracy. Consequently, the political history of Pakistan has portrayed that future of parliamentary form of democracy is insecure and it has been witnessed that few privileged class of people has always hijacked the democracy in Pakistan. In the election process the turnout of 30% of the population of the voting makes the validity of the election process very much doubtful because as per the democratic principles this percentage does not represents the whole population. The democratic history of Pakistan has witnessed that parliamentary system has become the game court where the fallacies and evils such as horse-trading,

king-making and lack of accountability and transparency has become the common practice in the assemblies. The soul of democracy the obligation of becoming answerable to the authority and public. The democratic system provides such a form of government where the rights of the people are protected but unfortunately in the democratic system of Pakistan, the rights of the common people are denied in all sphere of life. The Pakistan has always experienced autocratic form of democracy, where family oriented political parties has always ruled the Pakistan in the name of democracy. This democratic forms of governments are running 167 countries of the world and Pakistan is one of those countries. Under the 1973 constitution of the country, different forms of democracies prevailed in the country. Some were established under the dictators and some were the mixture of civilian and dictators. (Shah, 2013)

According to Quaid-e-Azam Mohammad Ali Jinnah,

“Pakistan is made for the betterment of the people living in it. People will themselves select their Leader and it’s the responsibility of the leader to fulfill the needs of the people and word day and night for this Motherland”

The people of Pakistan have been always struggling for the better of the Pakistan and the democratic form of government is the right choice for the better government but due to bad ruling of democratic governments, the democracy could not get hold its footings and it has been derailed off and on by the privileged class of people and bad political leadership (Waqas, 2014).

In the history of democracy of Pakistan Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto has worked a lot for the revival and sustainability of the democracy. According to him;

“The people of Pakistan deserve better fortune when it comes to Democracy. It is a great nation and Democracy is the best system for this nation. Let the democracy prevail and see the Nation flourish in the front of your eyes’

Currently, there is a royal form of democracy, where people are denied of justice, people are denied of basic rights, government policies are made under bureaucratic desks, there is no merit in posting the right person at right position, there is no transparency and accountability of public expenditure, there is no rule of law, there is massive corruption in all government sectors. The real solution of these fallacies and evils in our democratic form of government lies in adopting Presidential form of democratic system in the country. But before, adopting this system, there is dire need to create more provinces in densely populated province especially in Punjab (Waqas, 2014).

It is universally known fact that in democratic process, the representatives of

political parties are elected by the people of the country through balloting secretes votes in the favor of the contesting political candidates for the seat of Member of National Assembly or Member of Provincial Assembly. As the Government is elected by the people, therefore, it can be said that government is of the people. But in the context of Pakistanis democratic scenario, the situation is quite opposite to the values and ethics of the democracy. In the democratic process of Pakistan, voters cast their votes for electing the Member of National and Provincial Assembly through secret ballots. The members of National Assembly elect Prime Minister through secret ballots and similarly Members of Provincial Assembly elect Chief Ministers at their provinces also through secret ballots. The Prime Minister appoints the Ministers and Advisor at Federal level and Chief Minister appoint the Ministers at Provincial levels.

This study has focused its research on analyzing the essence of democracy, as to how far the essence of democracy .i.e. Government by People, Government of the People and Government for the people; is observed in true spirit of democracy in the democratic set up of Pakistan? The research has analyzed the essence of democracy on the basis of three factors i.e Demographic, Economical and Social situations of the people of Pakistan. The study has also analyzed the success or failure of parliamentary form of democracy since its introduction in the country

Research Methodoly

The study has use primary and secondary sources of data. For the primary source, the data has been gathered from the common targeted voters through random survey and for the secondary source data has been gather from the government website and other published material by different authors in the magazines and research journals.

During the survey, the common voters have been personally contacted by the data collector to ask constructed questions and answers marked by the collector. The data have been collected from two targeted areas; 5000 from rural areas and 5000 from urban areas. During the survey, the identity of targeted voters was kept secret for the sake of their safety.

Democracy in Rural Areas

According to the demographical situation, the population in the Pakistan is divided into two general categories i.e rural population- the people in the rural areas and urban population – the people living in cities and suburban areas. According to the statistics given by the Bureau of statistics of Pakistan, 70% population is residing in rural area and 30% population residing in urban areas.

Socially the people residing in the rural areas are under strong social influence of Landlords, Religious & Spiritual Leaders and Malik's. In that social bondage, they are unable to exercise their free will of determination in casting their votes in the election process. As they are living in area, therefore it must honor the words or sayings of these influential landlords, spiritual leaders, no matter how far they are good in their character. These influential people usually mollify the common voters by offering the dreams of petty benefits, if they cast vote in their favor. If they don't then they may face music of anger and difficult to live in their controlled territory. In other words, the common voters in rural areas are socially dependent on these influenced people; therefore, they can't dare to cast their votes against them.

Economically, the income of the people residing in rural area are totally dependent on the agriculture lands. They are earning their livelihoods by cultivating their lands. There are big landlords, medium landlord and small landlords. But most of them are

farmers of the landlords and their income dependent upon the labor work available in the vicinity of that area. Therefore, these influential landlords have got much influence on their livelihood resources in that area. Under such situation, it has become harder for the common voters to cast their votes with their free will in the election process.

Keeping in view above prevailing facts in rural areas, it can be concluded that 70% population residing in rural areas are socially and economically slaves to these Landlords and spiritual leaders, who are controlling the rural areas with the iron hands. In this situation, the common voters are socially and economically are slaves to these influential people and it is impossible to ascertain that the voters in the rural areas are able to exercise their votes with their free will of determination. Thus the essence of democracy i.e government of the people, for the people and by the people cannot be observed in any manner.

It has been observed from the study that common voters has expressed their pathetic situation in exercising their free will of determination to cast their votes in the election. In addition to that it is also found that the voters are also being bribed and threatened of dire consequences if they do not cast their votes in their favor. Moreover, these landlords having administrative and political influence in their constituencies' areas, use different rigging techniques to get winning result in their favor.

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Democracy in Urban Areas

According to the population statics provided by the Pakistan statistics bureau, the urban areas of Pakistan constitutes 30% population of the country, where the people belonging to different communities are residing in the various urban cities of Pakistan. The urban areas are mostly populated with middle and rich class of people. There is also poor class of people residing in the suburban areas. In urban areas, most of the people are educated and employed in government and private organization, They possesses enough political sense of awareness but most of the people remain at home and don't show their interest to go polling station for casting their votes. Because, they believe that these politicians are self-interested and their voting does not make any difference against them. The study has collected 5000 survey samples from the people residing in the urban areas. It has been found from the target population that most of the voters are exercising their free will of determination to cast their votes in favor of the proposed candidates. As the people residing in urban areas are educated therefore, it is very difficult by candidates to allure the voters to get favor without counting the credibility and character of the candidate.

There are certain areas in cities, where some political parties have got control through their militant wings and they use their militant wings to threaten the local residents of their dominant areas to cast their votes in their favorable candidates. In either case, they can be targeted in any way. These militant wings of political parties have made their dominant area as “**No Go Areas**”. It is also reported that these militant wing of political parties use different rigging techniques in the polling station established in their dominant areas. It is also learnt that these polling stations are established without any proper consideration of the population

and these are usually established in the small streets of that “No Go Areas”, where the militant of these political parties easily rigged the election process at gun point.

It has been observed from the study in urban areas that most of the voters are not interested to cast their votes in the elections and they remain at their homes. They perceived that there is no credible candidate whom they vote for and their votes has no importance in making any difference in the electing the candidates, because there is always rigging in the election.

Democracy in Political Parties

According to the statistics provided by the Election Commission of Pakistan, there are 8 political parties in Pakistan. These political parties are formed by the political leaders who belong to rich class family and the party belongs to their family members only. No one other than their family member can be a partly leader in any circumstances. If the leader of the political party dies then his son or daughter must takes over as a Leader of the party ignoring the loyalties, sacrifices and commitment of other senior party leaders. It is indeed great dilemma in our country that every political party is claiming to be true protector of the democracy in the country but it is regrettable to say that no political party is observing democratic norms and ethics within their party. Any political party, who is not observing democratic norms and values in their party, cannot be called democratic political party. Since the introduction of parliamentary form of democracy in the country, it has been observed that none of these political parties has held any proper election within their parties. No party member or leader can dare to criticize the wrongdoings of senior political leaders in the party. The decision of heads of the party is the final one to be followed by the all leaders of the political parties, no matter how far it is wrong. The most alarming thing

learnt from the study is that, the party tickets for contesting the elections are being given to only those party leaders who pays more money in the name of donations to the party and that usually be in millions of rupees. Obviously, the political candidate who paid for obtaining the ticket would first serve his own pocket rather than serving the people of his constituencies.

Moreover, it is well-known fact that elected members in National and Provincial assemblies frequently change their loyalties for their personal gains and other illegal benefits from the ruling party government. In this regard, the history of these political leaders is filled with many scandals of changing loyalties from one part to another party. The most alarming matter is that 90% of elected assemblies' members are uneducated or simply graduated from the universities of Pakistan. The assemblies and senate of Pakistan are mostly filled with feudal and business class representative of the parties. According to the study 95% parliamentary members are from the feudal and business class families and most of their personal history is filled with criminal and corruption back grounds. Their leadership approach is to how rule the people rather than to serve the people. It has been observed throughout the democratic history of Pakistan that they have always served their own interests rather than the interests of common people whom they have voted for the national and provincial legislation bodies.

On the basis of obtained information through survey from the targeted common voters, it can be concluded that the political parties in Pakistan have failed to adopt the democratic principles and values within their parties and most of the family political leaders use authoritarian form of leadership within their party. Therefore, according to the universal democratic principles, any political party which does not follow the democratic principles cannot be called a democratic party.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is concluded from the study that, demographically, economically and socially, parliamentary form of democracy is not suitable to our country. The study has proved that due to the above discussed critical factors, our parliamentary form of democratic system has failed to represents the real democracy in the country and yield any productive result for the development of nation. Moreover, the prevailing democratic system is dominated by rich and feudal class of people and the rich is getting richer and poor is getting poor. It is high time to adopt presidential form of democracy.

On the basis of the study, it is recommended that **Presidential Form of Democracy** should be adopted for the future survival of the country. In this regard, there are many models of presidential form of democracy adopted in the Asian nation, such as in **Turkey, Singapore, Indonesia and Taiwan**. Our country can adopt one of the model which may be suitable to our country that represents the true essence of democracy. Moreover, following recommendations are suggested to adopt the real democratic system in Pakistan.

- **The independent election commission with viable leadership may be established to conduct a fair and free election in the country.**
- **Separate schedule of conducting election may be charted out for each province, such as two days for each province for Provincial and National Assembly election.**
- **NADRA offices may be used as Polling stations at division and district levels during the election.**
- **The Electronic Voting System may be introduced at NADRA offices at each division and district levels, where the voters are allowed to cast their votes by entering their**

NIC card numbers and thumb recognition system.

- **The army may be deployed at all polling stations in the country to make feel the common voters safe and free while casting their votes.**

In continuation of this study, the author is working on to exploring the viable model of presidential form of democracy for Pakistan.

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